

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Annotation.

The article talks about phraseology, their place in the study of the linguistic landscape of the world, the ancient views and traditions of peoples. The stability of meaning in the author's phraseology, the fact that the structure is used as a stable and ready-made unit is a tradition that has already gone out of memory, it is of great importance as a reserve that preserves traditions, they not only create an opportunity to familiarize with the national worldview, but also with the way of life that has remained in the history of peoples. gives conclusions about the formation of phraseological units specific and suitable for a certain ethnos through linguo-creative thinking.

Key words.

phraseological unity, linguistic landscape of the world, cognitive linguistics, pragmatics, linguistic culture.

Nowadays, phraseology has turned from the level of a department of lexicology into one of the independent disciplines of linguistics with its own research object and method. The science of phraseology is related to history, literary studies, linguistic country studies and a number of other disciplines of linguistics such as lexicology, semantics, grammar, phonetics, stylistics, language history, etymology, text linguistics and general linguistics. Phraseology is a very complex phenomenon, and its study requires a specific method, as well as a number of other disciplines, such as lexicology, grammar, stylistics, phonetics, history, logic, and country studies.

Analyzing only the structural-semantic features of this language phenomenon (phraseme), it is not possible to reveal all its features, because phrasemes, as a nominative unit of the language, represent and reflect the linguistic landscape of the world, have a unique semantic, differ by the occurrence of functional properties.

The fact that phrasemes "come into the world" on the basis of a secondary designation, express meaning through words, and are used as a unique unit in cases where it is difficult to name, requires to see them as a complete linguistic unit.

Lexical units involved in the formation of the meaning of phrases, as we noted in the previous chapter, serve to fill the semantic reserve of the language with their own unique meanings. The people create units that are short in form but have deep expressive meaning in order to name and express new concepts, to visualize different social situations, or to open different aspects of existing concepts and realities. Of course, these are expressions that have passed through many years of experience of that nation, and are understandable for that nation, people, and people. These phraseological units usually not only simply name something, but also assess its connotative (stylistic) coloring, the speaker's attitude to existence, and therefore the phraseological meaning is a specific meaning in the language.

In addition, phraseological expressions have been a unique tool for studying the linguistic landscape of the world, the views and traditions of peoples that have existed since ancient times. The stability of meaning in them, their use as a stable and ready-made unit is of great importance as a reserve that preserves customs and traditions that have already been forgotten. They not only make it possible to introduce the national worldview, but also introduce the way of life left in the history of peoples.

Of course, in this process, simple meaning-creating mechanisms, i.e., analogy, simile, and transfer methods are used. All this is realized on the basis of the national-cultural mentality of a certain nation and creates a phraseological picture of the "world" of that nation. The important thing is that they are a very important "weapon" in revealing the national-cultural characteristics of peoples. Because, according to the definition of the great linguist W. Von Humboldt, each language has its own "own" internal construction, form, i.e., "own will, voluntary path" in organizing thinking and is connected with the spirit of that nation. His famous statement "My language is my soul, my soul is my language"²² is still the basis of this burning.

The following thoughts of the famous Russian psychologist A.N. Leontev are consistent with the ideas of V. Humboldt: "Each nation's outlook and understanding of the world is based on its system of subject knowledge, social stereotypes and cognitive tables. That is why the human consciousness is always

²² Гумбольдт В. фон. Избранные труды по языкознанию. – М.: Прогресс, 1984. – С. 103

ethnically determined, the worldview of one nation cannot be simply "recoded" into the language of another nation's culture.²³

V. Supporters of the Humboldt theory include American scientists E. Sepir, B. Whorf, V. Humboldt's theory propagator L. Weisgerber points out that there are significant differences between languages in the formation of the linguistic landscape of the world. Such differences mainly emphasize the fact that they occur in the naming of objects, in word combinations with a linguistic and cultural component, and in phraseological expressions.²⁴

However, for the sake of justice, it should be noted here that there are not a few scientists who object to such views. Famous Russian scientist, Academician N.M. According to Shansky, "Exaggerating the differences between languages" is one of the many stubborn errors, the feature of language perception of the world is exaggerated.²⁵ There are a number of cases that confirm the objections of Academician N.M. Shansky. Firstly, the system-mechanism of naming in languages is basically similar, and secondly, there is a number of commonalities in the lexical, phraseological, inventory - stock of languages. We all know very well that communication is based on these analogies.

Any language unit has not only a nominative function, but also a means of expressing the historical, national-cultural treasure of the people, people, people who speak a certain language. Here, the role and importance of phraseological expressions in languages is incomparable. Because most of them are "watered" with nationality - identity as a secondary nominal unit. The importance of the various works of art created by each nation, be it in the form of paintings, sculptures or national architecture, in revealing the national characteristics of that nation is certainly recognized. At the same time, among the unique monuments, the uniqueness expressed in the existing language units - proverbs, wise sayings passed down from generation to generation, historical, scientific, and practical information is very valuable.

Their uniqueness lies in the fact that through them the unique concepts, feelings, moral rules, which have been sharpened and polished in the trials of life, and have reached this day, cannot be fully described by another monument. That is why the "treasure-reserve" of any language is the "treasure-reserve" of the nation.

²³ Леонтьев А.Н. Проблемы развития психики. – М.: Издательство МГУ, 1981. – С. 20

²⁴ Сепир Э. Избранные труды по языкознанию и культурологии – М.: Прогресс, 2001 – 200 с; Whorf B.L. Language, thought and reality: Selected writings of Benjamin Lee Whorf – Cambridge: The MIT press, 1956 – P. 246 – 270; Вайсгербер Й.Л. Родной язык и формирование духа / Пер. с нем., вступ. ст. и коммент. О.А.Радченко. Изд 2-е, испр. и доп. – М.: УРСС эдиториал, 2004. – 232 с.

²⁵ Шанский Н.М. Фразеология современного русского языка. Изд. 3-е, испр. и доп. – М.: Высшая школа, 1985. – 160 с.

Emotions expressed through language, assessments given to the objective world, are not realized through any means. The role of language elements in revealing the national-cultural world of peoples, in reaching its foundations, and in determining its specific aspects is indisputable.

For example, one of the beautiful qualities of the Uzbek people is hospitality. When a guest comes, no matter who he is, he is greeted with honor, a bright face, and sweet words. This situation is justified by a number of proverbs and proverbs such as "Guest is a special god", "Guest comes through the door, food comes through the hole". It is not possible to express such a vital concept in such a concise, simple and effective way through other linguistic and non-linguistic elements.

We all know the importance of pets in the social life and lifestyle of every nation. We can see how important the sheep, one of the domestic animals, is in the life of the Uzbek people. A number of phraseological expressions have arisen in connection with the sheep's nature and world: a sheep does not take a stick from its mouth, it is meek like a sheep... The language images created by phraseological expressions represent the national spirit, national intuition, feeling, represents perception and understanding of the world and serves this purpose.

Through the categories of intensification and deintensification in languages, there are cases of strengthening or weakening of linguistic signs, reducing or decreasing their quantity. A vivid manifestation of this situation is manifested in the emergence of phrasemes, their pragmatic relations with each other. We can clearly see the influence of the quantitative changes from the philosophical categories on the qualitative changes, in the example of idioms. They are formed as a new language unit in the semantic system of the language, being organically connected with the subjective-pragmatic categories such as naming, quality, quantity, evaluation, emotionality, imagery, description, expressiveness, which exist at the lexical level of the language, and are formed as a new unit with a quality indicator in the semantic system of the language.

The idea of "collapse" of the meaning of the words contained in the phrases put forward by Professor M.E. Umarmho'jaev requires a reconsideration of the multi-meaning concepts in the words. "The main feature that distinguishes polysemy from semantic confusion" - writes professor M.E. Umarmho'jaev, is the variety of designations of language units with independent meanings, or the so-called "empty meaning". Designates of polysemous words differ from each other in terms of more or less semantic relatedness, and they are expressed in different meanings of the corresponding word. It is difficult to talk about the separation of

the semantic relation features of the designat in the semantic decomposition of the word.²⁶

In fact, the semantic "collapse" of words into phrases can be a convenient tool for determining, on the one hand, the nominative meaning of the word and its status in the phrase, and on the other hand, the location of these units relative to each other.

From the analyzed examples, it should be noted that the method of this direction has both scientific and practical importance in a comprehensive study of the phraseological fund of the language. First of all, this concept has a scientific basis, being simple and convenient, and its universal feature makes it possible to thoroughly analyze the phraseological subsystem (tagsystem) of all languages. This method not only provides an opportunity to classify the phraseological fund of languages, but also serves as a necessary instrument to determine its limits, and most importantly, to study the "birth" or "birth" of phraseology in a language, under the influence of linguistic and extralinguistic factors, the process of turning a phrase into a phrase. . Such an analysis is carried out with the collective criteria mentioned in the above sections when determining the central and peripheral units of the phraseological system.

On the subject, the idea and method of determining the center and peripheral elements of the phraseological system, put forward by professor M.E. Umarho'jaev, is the basis for revealing not only that the subsystem has a systemic nature, but also that the language itself has a full systemic character²⁷. By approaching the language in this way, the ways of its development are studied, the special features of the language between systems, the process of transformation of system units from one system to another system unit are revealed.

At this point, it is necessary to mention the complementary feature of the complete lexical system of the language and the phraseological system, which is its system.

Many years of research conducted by linguists, the analysis of monolingual and multilingual phraseological dictionaries are the basis for our coming to the following conclusions:

I. Phraseological expressions did not appear in the language by chance, firstly, they were created to name objects and events that cannot be named and explained

²⁶ Шанский Н.М. Фразеология современного русского языка. Изд. 3-е, испр. и доп. – М.: Высшая школа, 1985. – 160 с.

²⁷ Умарходжаев М.Э. Центр и периферия во фразеологии. // Известия АН. Серия и литературы языка. – Москва, 1980. – С. 148

by the units of the lexical system, and secondly, they appeared in order to express, clarify or exaggerate the specific aspects of the named objects and events.

II. As noted by some linguists, they are not "extra" elements in the language, they are a phenomenon that fills the significant, necessary semantic "world" of the language.²⁸ Without such expressions, the language would be very "impoverished". There is no area in life where expressions are not used in their proper place. As proof of our opinion, we can show through the following examples that phraseological expressions are a unique communication tool for enriching the semantic world of the Uzbek language, naming objects and events, and expressing individual feelings.

1. When expressing the physiological state of a person:

- a) two faces are similar;
- b) like a cat falling into water;
- c) as if he would fall if he pulled his nose;
- d) the sun can be seen from his ears.

2. When expressing the negative characteristics of a person:

- a) within a brother-in-law;
- b) one screw is missing;
- c) not in his right mind.

3. When expressing a person's suffering:

- a) to fry in its own oil;
- b) die and rise again;
- c) take your own pain.

4. When expressing the internal state of a person:

- a) his eyes widened;
- b) was left on the throne (in the hospital);
- c) he disappears (in the hospital)
- d) you are blind and I am blind;
- e) there is no work left.

In general, the identification of the sources of formation of phraseological units has a much broader meaning than the etymological analysis of stable compounds. That is, it is a general philological problem, and determining the stages of formation of the oldest, first phraseological models is considered an important semiotic problem. Recently, Turkic scholars have started to study the same urgent problem. In particular, prof. G. According to Bayramov, expressing

²⁸ Никитин В.М. Проблема классификации фразеологизмов и их относительная устойчивость и варьирование // Проблема устойчивости и вариативности фразеологических единиц.– Тула, 1968.– Вып.1 – С. 68.

the phraseological meaning with a specific word is much older than giving it using a fixed or free combination. Because the formation of phraseological units belongs to later periods in the development of the language, while lexical units have been in effect since the beginning of the language.²⁹ For example, in Mahmud Kashgari, the word *andar yasama* means to take an oath.³⁰ Later, in Turkic languages, the affix *-har* was replaced by the word *ich*, and phraseological units such as *and ichdirmek*, *ant ichirmek* appeared.

Phraseology is composed of words, and the word is the main object studied by lexicology. Based on the sources of lexicology, it is possible to determine the nature of the components of phraseology and their linguistic level.

²⁹ Мокненко В.М. Историческая фразеология: этнография или лингвистика // Вопросы языкознания. 1973. № 2. – С. 32-33.

³⁰ Махмуд Қошғарий «Девону луғотит турк» II том. 402-бет.